

Environmental and Social Sustainability Development Evaluation in Mining Industry (Case study in Guinea and China)

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Abstract: One of the main global challenges that now affects all countries, either individually or collectively, is environmental concern. Metals and minerals are crucial to contemporary life and to the economic and social progress of our civilization. Human sustainability is correlated with environmental sustainability; the and economic, social, and environmental factors all play a role in sustainable development. In contrast to China's mining environmental impact, this study primarily focused on the sustainability of mining and its effects in Guinea. The Folchi approach is a crucial tool for environmental impact assessments (EIA). The Inner Mongolia Bayan Obo mine, the world's largest source of rare earth elements (REE), as well as three Guinean bauxite mines are used in this study to evaluate and quantify the environmental, social, and economic impact of mining activities. This paper also applies an improvement to the Folchi method in EIA. For each environmental component, numerous affecting aspects from mining operations were calculated, which may be classified as social interactions, air and water quality, flora, and wildlife, as well as public health and safety. Each influencing element was first assigned a magnitude for this reason, merely based on the range of potential outcomes. The impacts of each influencing element were then thoroughly quantified and normalized using a matrix of weighted factors that was generated. Weighted rates were then added to determine the total effect on each specific environmental component. Folchi technique was used in this instance to assess such environmental factors. The Environmental Impact Statement for the planned mining operation may thus be easily shown graphically. The study emphasizes the usefulness of using the model to accomplish the goal of sustainable mining. This study is significant from an environmental and socioeconomic standpoint, and mining environmental impact assessors, researchers, and Guinea's government should all take it into consideration.

Keywords: Mining Sustainable development, Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), Folchi method, Phillips mathematical model, health and safety, Open pit mines

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1. Introduction

The mining sector has always faced with social and environmental concerns[1]. On the one hand, the progress of Human civilization and the global economy depend on their products and services, but on the other, This field is notorious for its high death rates, human rights abuses, labor exploitation of miners, and other immoral practices[2]. Meeting current needs while avoiding to sacrifice the capacity of future civilizations to satisfy their own is the process of sustainable development[3]. But from the most basic to the finest items, mining is required to produce the things that are used in daily life and society. The production of pollution and by-products, however, is a substantial effect of mining(Robu et al., 2015; Slușer et al., 2017). One of the biggest producers in the world in this regard is the mining sector. Large-scale activities always produce this kind of waste. An important contributor to environmental damage is the disposal of waste produced by mining[6].

In reality, increased Bauxite mining in Guinea necessitates attention to environmental concerns and pollution control. As a result, one of the key concerns for a nation's sustainable growth is environmental conservation[7]. Although there are currently no restrictions on productivity capacity of mines, maintaining an appropriate environment is still essential for both miners and the general public[7].

Mining, Minerals and Sustainable Development (MMSD) study claims that, there are four main categories of mining waste[6]:

1. Overburden: rock and soil that are cleared away allowing accessibility to a mining deposit;
2. Waste rock: which is defined as rock containing minerals of insufficient commercial value;
3. Tailings: ground-up ore that is left behind after extraction and processing in the shape of a slurry of residues;
4. Heap leach wasted ore: After the mineral has been extracted, the rock which remains in a heap leach operation is known as Heap leach wasted ore.

Industry and technology have enhanced human understanding and raised living conditions over time, but they are also linked to environmental damage and pollution[8]. The environment may be changed most effectively and significantly by people[9]. They harm the environment in order to support human existence and also bring about beneficial and acceptable changes in the environment. As a result, people are the ones who cause and must control pollution[9]. Two fundamental components of development planning are industrial development and environmental sustainability. Industrial growth has to be founded on the idea of environmental sustainability in order to be sustainable[9]. Each nation's sustainable growth depends in large part on its interaction to the environment. The consequences of disregarding environmental concerns and natural resources are alarming. Environmental impact assessments (EIAs) are now required for industrial and mining operations in order to avoid and manage environmental issues[9].

Typically, environmental impact assessment (EIA) is referred to as a required assessment procedure that looks into and examines the environmental repercussions of human activity(Teodosiu et al., 2016; Robu et al., 2015). Environmental impact assessment is the process of identifying, calculating, evaluating, and minimizing the important side effects of the development initiatives, according to the International Association of Impact Assessment (IAIA)(*Business Environment Answers | PDF | Incineration | Environmental Impact Assessment*, n.d.; Robu et al., 2015; Projects & Development, 2020).

To determine quantitative or qualitative numerical figures for the effects on the environment, both quantitative and qualitative impact analysis techniques are utilized in the environmental impact assessment(Robu et al., 2015; Folchi, 2003).

As Mining activities in Guinea are getting more and more intense, because of its mineral potential (see fig. 4), The Government should pay more attention to the mining environmental Sustainability as the fig. 1 shows. Guinea is home

to a number of significant mining hotspots and this study is likely to quantify the impact of 3 Guinea’s Mining company on the environment.

Sustainable Development Management in Mining:

The company's sensitivity to the surrounding factors environmental, economic, and social determines its potential to achieve sustainability(Bogusz & Sulich, 2019; Araya et al., 2021). To put it another way, the company must first become eco-centric, after which it must become sustainability-focused. All of these tasks require significant work and take time[14].

A sustainable future depends on the wise management of ecosystems and natural resources(Governance, n.d.; Monjezi et al., 2009).

Environmental Management and Mining Governance proposes four crucial factors to take into account for effective environmental management in mining (see fig. 1):

Figure 1: Environmental management in mining[15]

Factor 1: Water

Efficaciously and fairly managing the quantity and quality of water resources for all users and the ecosystems they depend on [15][16][17]. Governments must control water consumption, water discharges, and water quality as well as the exploitation of important water resources at the watershed level.

Large volumes of water are used in mining operations to:

- Process ore;
- Camp supply operations
- Reduce dust
- Transfer the slurry

Factor 2: Mine Waste

Make that all mining waste, such as waste rock; tailing and associated facilities; used heap leach pads and facilities, sludge and precipitates from mineral recovery or water treatment; and dust are long-term physically and chemically stable[15][3][18].

In order to reduce danger and exposure to people, land, agriculture, plants, and animals, water systems and facilities must be constructed[19].

Factor 3: Emergency, readiness, and action

Involved parties should be prepared to prevent, manage, respond to, and recover from emergencies[15].

National governments must make sure that all parties who may be impacted by mines are aware of and prepared to address any hazards throughout the mine's life cycle as the fig. 2 shows [15][20].

Risk assessment; readiness and prevention plans; reaction plans; recovery plans; and crisis communications plans should all be included in emergency preparedness and response programs.

Figure 2: Mining and Emergency Management

Factor 4: Biodiversity

Safeguard ecosystems, biodiversity, and the benefits they offer.

A number of factors, including: loss of habitat; ecosystem fragmentation and degradation; soil, water, air, noise pollution and human population growth[15]; an increase in fishing, hunting, gathering, and clearing land for agriculture; and the unexpected introduction of invasive species, can be directly or indirectly impacted by mining projects on biodiversity and ecosystem services[18][21].

To prevent and reduce these effects, national governments should establish regulations that adhere to the mitigation hierarchy (see fig. 3).

Figure 3: Sustainable mine image with the bio and local content relationship

Guinea Mineral Resources:

Guinea's mining sector prospered throughout the colonial era. Among the minerals mined are bauxite, gold, diamonds, iron, and gold (see fig. 4)[22].

Due to ongoing instability, political unpredictability, and a lack of infrastructure, Guinea, which contains some of the greatest high-grade bauxite and iron ore deposits in the world, has largely been unable to capitalize on its mining resources[23].

More than a quarter of the world's bauxite deposits are located in Guinea, which also includes significant quantities of high-quality iron ore reserves, the majority of which are over 60% grade[22]. Since these reserves are mostly unexplored, mining firms have a lot of opportunities[23].

Figure 4: Guinea Mining Area by Substance

2. Research Methodology

Table 1: Mining environment categories and impact factors

No.	Mining environment	Impacting factors
1	Human health and safety	Alteration of area's potential resources
2	Social relationship	Exposition, visibility of the pit
3	Water quality	Interference with above-ground water
4	Air quality	Interference with underground water
5	Use of territory	Increase in vehicular traffic
6	Flora and fauna	Atmospheric Release of Gas and Dust
7	Above ground	Fly-rock
8	Underground	Noise
9	Landscape	Ground vibration
10	Noise	Employment and livelihood of local work force
11	Economy	Contribution in GDP

Table 2: Rating of environmental parameters in the case study of mines / Ranges of magnitude for impacting factors

Impacting Factors	Scenario	Magnitude	SMB	SOCIETE ALLIANCE GUINEENNE DE BAUXITE D'ALUMINE ET D'ALUMINIUM (AGB2A)	SOCIETE ASHAPURA GUINEA RESSOURCES (SGMF Projet)	Inner Mongolia Bayan Obo mine
1. Alteration of area's potential resources	Parks, protected areas	8-10				
	Urban area	6 – 8				
	wildlife, agro-diversity area, wood	3 – 6	6	6	6	4
	Industrial area	1 - 3				
2. Exposition, visibility of the pit	Can be seen from inhabited areas	6 – 10				
	Can be seen from main roads	2 – 6	6	5	6	5
	Not visible	1 - 2				
3. Interference with above-ground water	Interference with lakes and rivers	6 – 10				
	Interferences with non-relevant water system	3 – 6	5	6	7	2
	No interference	1 - 3				
4. Interference with underground water	Water table superficial and permeable grounds	5 – 10				
	Water table deep and permeable grounds	2 – 5	5	5	5	7
	Water table deep and un-permeable grounds	1 - 2				
5. Increase in vehicular traffic	Increase of 200%	6 – 10				
	Increase of 100%	3 – 6				
	No interference	1 - 3	7	6	5	8
6. Atmospheric Release of Gas and Dust	Free emissions in the atmosphere	7 – 10				
	Emissions around the given reference values	2 – 7				
	Emission well below the given reference values	1 - 2	7	8	10	5
7. Fly-rock	No blast design and no clearance procedures	9-10				
	Blast design and no clearance procedures	4-9				
	Blast design and clearance procedures	1 - 4	3	4	9	3
8. Noise	Peak air overpressure at 1km distance					
	<141 dB	8 – 10				
	<131 dB	4 – 8	6	7	6	3
	<121 dB	1 - 4				
9. Ground vibration	Cosmetic damage, above threshold	7 – 10				
	Tolerability threshold	3 – 7				
	Values under tolerability threshold	1 - 3	3	8	8	7

10. Employment of local work force	Job opportunities					
	High	7-10	8	7	7	8
	Medium	3-6				
	Low	1-2				
11. Contribution in GDP	Level of GDP contribution					
	High	7-10	7	5	5	8
	Medium	3-6				
	Low	1-2				

Table 3: Correlation matrix with values of the weighted influence of each impacting factor on each environmental component

Impacting factors	Environmental Components										
	Human health and safety	Social relationship	Water quality	Air quality	Use of territory	Flora and fauna	Above ground	Underground	Landscape	Noise	Economy
1. Alteration of area’s potential resources	Med 0.8	Min 0.77	Nil 0	Nil 0	Max 5.71	Min 0.63	Nil 0	Nil 0	Max 2.86	Nil 0	Nil 0
2. Exposition, visibility of the pit	Nil 0	Min 0.77	Nil 0	Nil 0	Med 2.86	Nil 0	Nil 0	Nil 0	Max 2.86	Min 2	Nil 0
3. Interference with above-ground water	Max 1.6	Nil 0	Max 4.44	Nil 0	Nil 0	Max 2.5	Med 6.67	Nil 0	Max 2.86	Nil 0	Nil 0
4. Interference with underground water	Min 0.4	Nil 0	Max 4.44	Nil 0	Nil 0	Nil 0	Nil 0	Med 6.67	Nil 0	Nil 0	Nil 0
5. Increase in vehicular traffic	Max 1.6	Max 3.08	Nil 0	Nil 0	Min 1.43	Max 2.5	Nil 0	Nil 0	Min 0.71	Nil 0	Nil 0
6. Atmospheric Release of	Max 1.6	Min 0.77	Min 1.11	Max 10	Nil 0	Max 2.5	Min 3.33	Nil 0	Min 0.71	Nil 0	Nil 0

**Gas and
Dust**

7. Fly-rock	Max	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Med	Nil	Nil	Nil	N	Nil
	1.6	0	0	0	0	1.25	0	0	0	0	0
8. Noise	Med	Max	Nil	Nil	Nil	Min	Nil	Nil	Nil	Max	Nil
	0.8	3.08	0	0	0	0.63	0	0	0	8	0
9. Ground vibration	Max	Med	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Min	Nil	Nil	Nil
	1.6	1.54	0	0	0	0	0	3.33	0	0	0
10. Employment and livelihood of local work force	Nil	N	Max								
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.67
11. Contribution in GDP	Nil	Min									
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.33
TOTAL	10										

2.1. Study Area description

Three significant Guinean bauxite open-pit mining companies were initially applied the Folchi method, which are SMB; AGB2A ; ASHAPURA GUINEA RESSOURCES and then in one Chinese open-pit mining which is Bayan Obo Mine [7].

2.1.1. Guinea's Bauxite Mining**2.1.1.1. SMB**

Société Minière de Boké (SMB) is a mining company founded in 2014. It is the result of a strategic alliance with winning shipping, UMS and Shandong Weiqia, number 1 in alumina production in China. SMB is a Guinean-Chinese company which deals with the mining of bauxite in the area of Boké, sub-prefecture of Tanéné, Dabiss, Kolabougni and malapouya, in the district of Kaboe and obtained its operating permit on June 10, 2015, its 1st ton of bauxite was released on July 20, 2015, it has a daily production capacity of 82,200 tons, a monthly output of 2,500,000 tons, and an annual output of 30,000,000 tons, fig. 5 describes its Mining Operations Schematic.

The SMB Company has built two (2) ports (Dapulon and Katougouma), the port of Dapulon is shared with companies such as CDM Chine, AMR and GDM (before the commissioning of its port in Kataméné).

The company has considered mitigation strategies for mud pollution, dust blow-offs, and reduced blow-offs from mining roads (see table 4). 99 cisterns regularly irrigate mining roads, in the mines and around the living quarters.

The speed limit on mining roads is 40 km/h, and the speed limit in mines is 30 km/h. HSSE agents regularly conduct speed checks on mining roads and in mines using mobile and fixed speed cameras.

Sampling campaigns for IN-SITU analyses of water from streams, boreholes and wells in the various villages within the consortium permit are carried out.

At the very beginning of the exploitation of the bauxite blocks, according to SMB officials, demonstrations by the neighbouring communities impacted by the project were recurrent; nowadays, thanks to the consideration of local development concerns and the good collaboration that they have created and maintained, the social and peaceful climate.

Figure 5: Mining Operations Schematic

Table 4: Monitoring table to support SMB chosen numbers in table 2:

Impacting Factors	Monitoring Results	Mitigation Measures	Frequency of Monitoring	Location
Accident	The HSSEC Department manages monitoring.	Raising awareness of behavior and conduct and compliance with safety rules, the correct and compulsory wearing of PPE, the periodic inspection of machinery and equipment, the breathalyzer, the installation of road signs, etc.	Less frequent	Sites and workshops

Air Pollution	<p>Given the enormous fleet of wheeled equipment, the distance travelled, and the absence of oversight of the watering of mine roads, the air is severely contaminated by dust. This phenomenon is also linked to the lack of water in the rivers.</p>	<p>Regular watering of the roads practiced, limitation of the speed of vehicles in built-up areas.</p>	<p>Not punctual and regular.</p>	<p>Mine and mining road and sometimes in the agglomerations</p>
Noise Pollution	<p>The existence of harmful and very loud noises in places</p>	<p>Good review of machines and equipment, the use of individual and collective protective equipment (ear plugs, ear headphones, cabin etc.</p>	<p>Not punctual and regular</p>	<p>On the mine field, The welding workshop, carpentry etc...</p>
Waste Disposal	<p>The company generates waste</p>	<p>Implementation of a waste management system and sorting, with the aim of destroying, transforming and/or recycling them.</p>	<p>Permanent</p>	<p>On Mines field, kitchen, garrages, workshops, Office etc...</p>
Water pollution	<p>Mining operations contaminate water sources with dust, wastewater, and red mud that pours into the riverbed during strip mining and infrastructure building.</p>	<p>Proceed with the watering of mining roads, set up evacuation channels and barriers (dikes) at the level of watercourses.</p>	<p>Not regular</p>	<p>Mining Road, Mines, Garrages or Workshops</p>
Soil Erosion	<p>The exploitation activities on the mining plateaus as well as lateritic quarries, etc., contribute to soil deterioration.</p>	<p>Rehabilitate and reforest exploited areas.</p>	<p>after 50% exploitation of the mine</p>	<p>Mining plateaus, quarries, etc.</p>
		<p>The protection of the environment and living species are managed in accordance with the ESMP (environmental and social management plan), namely the</p>		

Biodiversity	<p>Biodiversity is managed according to the environmental and social management plan resulting from the environmental and social impact study</p> <p>protection of living beings and the conservation of their living environment in their natural state, the establishment of migration corridors, conservation and protection of classified forests, reforestation campaigns, etc.</p>	Permanent	Sites in operation.
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Local Development Management	<p>The contribution for the supply of the FODEL account is paid according to the annual turnover of the company equal to 0.5%, 15% is paid to the ANAFIC account (the national community financing agency), also ANIES.</p> <p>There are also voluntary actions of companies taking into account the impact or the pressing need of the community (the reprofiling of community roads, donations of water drilling, donations, etc.)</p>	Within the villages impacted by the project.
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2.1.1.2. Alliance Guinéenne de Bauxite, d'Alumine, et d'Aluminium (AGB2A)

Alliance Guinéenne de Bauxite, d'Alumine, et d'Aluminium (AGB2A) is a consortium that includes two companies holding operating permits, which are:

- Axis Minerals Resources holds a bauxite mining permit covering an area of 428 km² in the prefectures of Boffa, Dubreka and Fria, located in the sub-prefectures of Lisso, Tamita, Tanènè and Tormelin.
- The Guinean Brain touch Company located in the Boffa area, sub-prefecture of Tamita, Lisso District of Gbasaya covers an area of 175.51 km², holds an operating permit.

Axis and GBT have set up a consortium called Alliance Guinéenne de Bauxite, d'Alumina, et d'Aluminium (AGB2A). This consortium is mainly composed of Guinean and international partners, AGB2A was created to develop high-grade bauxite mining and export activities (+40% alumina and <4% silica) from both exploitation permits (Axis/GBT) holding cumulatively more than 260,000,000 tons of bauxite in Guinea.

The mining route from GBT to Kokaya port is 17 km and the distance from Axis mine to Kokaya port is 45 km (see fig. 6).

Figure 6: Mining Road and Kokaya Port

2.1.1.3. ASHAPURA GUINEA RESSOURCES (SGMF Project)

Ashapura Guinea Resources SARL is a Guinean Bauxite mining company, which holds an exploration permit for Bauxite in the prefectures of Boffa and Dubréka, the permit covers an area of 402 km² (see table 5), its reserves are estimated at 326 million tons of bauxite with an estimated lifespan of 35 years and their bauxite has an average of 46% in Al₂O₃ with an annual production estimated at ten million tons.

The permit is located in western Guinea, in the prefectures of Boffa and Dubréka. It covers the CRDs of Tamita, Tanènè, Ouassou and Bady. The permit is accessible by the national Conakry-Dubréka-Boffa for an approximate distance of 100 km.

Table 5: The geographical coordinates of the permit

No	Latitude (N)	Longitude (W)	Area
1	10°15'0.0''	13°50'45.0''	
2	10°15'0.0''	13°30'0.0''	402 Km ²
3	10°9'15.0''	13°30'0.0''	
4	10°9'15.0''	13°50'45.0''	

2.1.2. Chinese’s Rare Earth Element mining

2.1.2.1. The REE-Fe-Nb ore deposit in Bayan Obo:

The Bayan Obo REE-Nb-Fe deposit is located in Inner Mongolia, 135 km northwest of Baotou, near the northernmost point of the North China Kraton (110°E, 41°47'N)[24]. It is a massive hydrothermally generated rare earth element (REE), ferrous, and niobium ore deposit. Prof. Ding Daoheng made the initial discovery of it as a deposit of iron in 1927[25]. Approximately 1.5 Bt, 1 Mt, and 48 Mt are the total estimated reserves of Fe (average grade Fe 35 wt%), Nb (average grade 0.13 wt%)[24], and REE (average grade REO 6 wt%). The biggest known REE ore deposit in the world is there[25]. Fig. 7 displays the mining region of Bayan Obo.

The Bayan Obo ore has 170 minerals and 71 elements, and the dispersion size is adequate. The mineral symbiotic relationship is complicated and intimate, and one element may be present in more than ten different minerals. More

than 90% of the rare earth elements found in ore are present as independent minerals, with the remaining 4% to 7% scattered in fluorite and iron minerals. There are a total of 15 different types of rare earth minerals, although bastnaesite [(Ce,La,Nd)(CO₃)F] and monazite [(Ce,La,Nd)PO₄] with a ratio of 7:3 or 6:4 are the most common ones[26]. Magnetite and hematite are the major Fe-ore minerals[24][25].

Figure 7: mining area of Bayun Obo mine

2.1.2.2 Bayan Obo Intelligent safety and security monitoring Management:

With the application of advance technologies such as open-pit mining production process digitization, driverless stope transportation and remote mining control, new requirements are forward for modern mine production safety. The Bayan Obo iron mine safety, temporary control system adopts accurate three-dimensional map positioning; the independent wireless communication system, geological monitoring and independent. The mine road monitoring system has realized the production safety temporary control under the modern open-pit mines adopt a large number of unmanned and automatic production modes.

2.2. Methodology:

Phillips Environmental Sustainability Mathematics (PESM) Model, in contrast to the Folchi approach for environmental factorization and indexing[27], serves as the foundation for the present study's research methodology[28][7]. Additionally, data analysis in PESM has utilized the Folchi method [29][9].

2.2.1. Folchi Method

The Folchi approach was developed scientifically to quantify the environmental effect of mining operations (drilling, blasting, and collecting minerals)[30]. Despite earlier research indicating that the analysis is accurate, authorized entities can boost the accuracy of data collecting [29].

Table 1 represents different mining environments and the elements that influence them. Mining environment categories are included in the first column, and mining affecting factors are listed in the second. All potential environmental factors related to mining operations are mentioned in it. For a brief process visual, the detailed process of the Folchi method is shown in Fig. 8[31].

The scope of environmental, social, and economic elements is depicted in Table 2. There are three categories of projected affecting variables for each mining company: intense, medium, and low. According to the real contribution of the environmental component, the points are assigned. Information will be gathered from the residential areas and mining professionals of the different four distinct mining companies.

Table 3 displays the correlation matrix of the components' magnitudes and influencing variables. The correlation matrix reproduces the extent to which environmental factors are endangered. Maximum (Max), Med (Median), and Minimum (Min) numbers represent the potential contributions of each particular category or component, respectively[28]. In Table 3, the content and category with no meaningful associations or that is insignificant are denoted with zero (Nil).

Figure 8: Complete process of the Folchi method in form of successive steps

2.2.2. Phillips Environmental Sustainability Mathematics (PESM) Model

Using magnitude recognition values from Folchi, the mathematical model of Phillips is utilized to assess whether the different mines have an unsustainable or sustainable impact on the environment[32][33].

The model is divided into two sections: the environment and human needs. Equation (E1) measures the environmental contribution as follows:

$$E = \frac{[(\sum A_{max} - (A_1 + A_2)) + (\sum B_{max} - \sum B) + (\sum H_{max} - \sum H) + (\sum L_{max} - (L_1 + L_2 + L_3 + L_4))]}{\sum A_{max} + \sum B_{max} + \sum H_{max} + \sum L_{max}} \quad (E1)$$

$$E = \frac{[(\sum A_{max} - \sum A) + (\sum B_{max} - \sum B) + (\sum H_{max} - \sum H) + (\sum L_{max} - \sum L)]}{\sum A_{max} + \sum B_{max} + \sum H_{max} + \sum L_{max}} \quad (E1)$$

The acronyms "A" for atmosphere, "B" for biosphere, "H" for hydrosphere, and "L" for lithosphere are used to denote the four primary components of the environment in the equation (E1): $E(t) = (A + B + H + L)$. In terms of time, sphere fluctuation is quantified[28][34]. $E(t) = [E_0 \leq E \leq E_{max}]$ examines the sub-spherical functioning and maximum limitations of the maximum safe environmental anthropological system. E represents the environment's circular development,

adaptation, regeneration, and repair with respect to time t. According to the formula $E = \frac{(E_{max} - \sum E)}{\sum E_{max}}$, with dividing the

result by the maximum environmental value and subtracting the actual contribution of environmental components from the maximum environmental value, the level of the environment is determined[28][34].

A human need is the second component of the model, and it is shown in the Equation (E2):

$$H_{NI} = \frac{(H_{NI1} + H_{NI2}) + (H_{NI3_{max}} - H_{NI3_{actual}})}{\sum H_{NI_{max}}} \quad (E2)$$

$$H_{NI} = \frac{(\sum H_{NI_{max}} - \sum H_{NI})}{\sum H_{NI_{max}}} \quad (E2)$$

In the equation (E2), H_{NI} accounts for human needs or socioeconomic factors; specifically, the collection of (Human Health and Safety + Social Interaction + Quality of Life + Economy), where H_{NI1} , H_{NI2} , and H_{NI3} denote three components, respectively[28][34]. The resources and environmental contribution to human life and survival are shown by the human needs' components $H_{NI}(t) = [H_{NI} \leq H_{NI} \leq H_{NI \max}]$ [30].

The following step is to determine the link between the environment, socioeconomic conditions, and the four mining Company once the environmental and socioeconomic parameters have been calculated. The last stage of this model clarified the sustainability level and the workable working environment in each of the four mines. $S(t) = E(t) - H_{NI}(t)$ calculates sustainability by subtracting the human interest and needs value from the environmental value. The sustainable and beneficial influence on the environment will be recognised if $E(t) > H_{NI}(t) \Leftrightarrow S(t) > 0$, and a negative and unsustainable influence on the environment will be reported if $E(t) \leq H_{NI}(t) \Leftrightarrow S(t) \leq 0$ [35][28][34].

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Result

In the current study, environmental information linked to the abovementioned four case studies was gathered, and each open-pit activity that has an impact on the environment was assessed using the Folchi approach. Furthermore, every aspect that would have an influence on the proposed mining operation was evaluated using the magnitude ranges indicated in Table 2. Each mining case value in Tables 2 and 3 may be multiplied to obtain the final score for each environmental component. The total influence on each environmental component for each case study is determined by adding the weighted magnitudes of all the contributing elements or (impacting factors) (see tables 6, 7, 8, 9).

The SMB Bauxite Mine's most significant impacts had score values of 70, 61, 60, 59, 59, and 59, respectively, on air quality, use of the area, noise, landscape, social relationships, and flora and fauna and the monitoring table 4 is the chosen

numbers in table 2. In the AGB2A Mine, environmental components of Air quality; Above ground; Social relationship; Noise; Human health and safety; and Flora and fauna had score values of 80, 67,67, 66, 64, 63 respectively. The environmental factors that are most impacted in **ASHAPURA GUINEA RESSOURCES** mine are Air quality; Above ground; Flora and fauna; and Human health and safety with scores of 100, 80, 74, 74, respectively. Lastly, the environmental factors that have the biggest impact on Inner Mongolia Bayan Obo mine are economy and underground with 80 and 70 score values, respectively (Fig. 9). Phillips Environmental Sustainability Mathematics (PESM) model uses the summing of each category to determine if the connection between mining and environmental sustainability is sustainable or not.

The two final factors, local forces' means of subsistence and GDP contributions are both economic in nature. Due to the high employment rate of local residents, Table 2's SMB mines weighting of local details' livelihood is 8; similarly, the contribution to GDP received 7 points due to the high contribution. Due to the high employment rate of residents, the weighting of local livelihood in the AGB2A Mine is 7 and the GDP contribution received 5 points for its medium contribution. Because of the high employment rate of locals, the weighting of local livelihood in the ASHAPURA GUINEA RESSOURCES mine is 7, while the GDP contribution earned 5 points due to its medium weight. Last but not least, the Inner Mongolia Bayan Obo mine's weighting of local livelihood is 8 due to the high employment rate of its population, and its high contribution to GDP got 8 points. It's also important to be aware that the Chinese government provides full backing for the Bayan Obo mine, which significantly boosts its economic position.

Table 6: Final scoring for each environmental component in SMB mine

Impacting factors	Environmental Components										
	Human health and safety	Social relationship	Water quality	Air quality	Use of territory	Flora and fauna	Above ground	Underground	Landscape	Noise	Economy
	HNI1	HNI2	H1	A1	L1	B1	L2	L3	L4	A2	HNI3
1. Alteration of area's potential resources	4.8	4.62	0	0	34.26	3.78	0	0	17.16	0	0
2. Exposition, visibility of the pit	0	4.62	0	0	17.16	0	0	0	17.16	12	0
3. Interference with above-ground water	8	0	22.2	0	0	12.5	33.35	0	14.3	0	0
4. Interference with	2	0	22.2	0	0	0	0	33.35	0	0	0

underground											
water											
5. Increase in vehicular traffic	11.2	21.56	0	0	10.01	17.5	0	0	4.97	0	0
6.	11.2	5.39	7.77	70	0	17.5	23.31	0	4.97	0	0
Atmospheric Release of Gas and Dust											
7. Fly-rock	4.8	0	0	0	0	3.75	0	0	0	0	0
8. Noise	4.8	18.48	0	0	0	3.78	0	0	0	48	0
9. Ground vibration	4.8	4.62	0	0	0	0	0	9.99	0	0	0
10.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	53.36
Employment and livelihood of local work force											
11.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.31
Contribution in GDP											
TOTAL	52	59	52	70	61	59	57	43	59	60	77

Table 7: Final scoring for each environmental component in AGB2A Mine

Impacting factors	Environmental Components										
	Human health and safety	Social relationship	Water quality	Air quality	Use of territory	Flora and fauna	Above ground	Underground	Landscape	Noise	Economy
	HNI1	HNI2	H1	A1	L1	B1	L2	L3	L4	A2	HNI3
1. Alteration of area's potential resources	4.8	4.62	0	0	34.26	3.78	0	0	17.16	0	0

2. Exposition, visibility of the pit	0	3.85	0	0	14.3	0	0	0	14.3	10	0
3. Interference with above-ground water	9.6	0	26.64	0	0	15	40.02	0	17.16	0	0
4. Interference with underground water	2	0	22.2	0	0	0	0	33.35	0	0	0
5. Increase in vehicular traffic	9.6	18.48	0	0	8.58	15	0	0	4.26	0	0
6. Atmospheric Release of Gas and Dust	12.8	6.16	8.88	80	0	20	26.64	0	5.68	0	0
7. Fly-rock	6.4	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0
8. Noise	5.6	21.56	0	0	0	4.41	0	0	0	56	0
9. Ground vibration	12.8	12.32	0	0	0	0	0	26.64	0	0	0
10. Employment and livelihood of local work force	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	46.69
11. Contribution in GDP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.65
TOTAL	64	67	58	80	57	63	67	60	59	66	63

Table 8: Final scoring for each environmental component in ASHAPURA GUINEA RESSOURCES (SGMF Project)

TOTAL	74	63	64	100	59	74	80	60	65	60	63
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Table 9: Final scoring for each environmental component in Inner Mongolia Bayan Obo mine

Impacting factors	Environmental Components										
	Human health and safety	Social relationship	Water quality	Air quality	Use of territory	Flora and fauna	Above ground	Underground	Landscape	Noise	Economy
	HNI1	HNI2	H1	A1	L1	B1	L2	L3	L4	A2	HNI3
1. Alteration of area’s potential resources	3.2	3.08	0	0	22.84	2.52	0	0	11.44	0	0
2. Exposition, visibility of the pit	0	3.85	0	0	14.3	0	0	0	14.3	10	0
3. Interference with above-ground water	3.2	0	8.88	0	0	5	13.34	0	5.72	0	0
4. Interference with underground water	2.8	0	31.1	0	0	0	0	46.69	0	0	0
5. Increase in vehicular traffic	12.8	24.64	0	0	11.44	20	0	0	5.68	0	0
6. Atmospheric Release of Gas and Dust	8	3.85	5.55	50	0	12.5	16.65	0	3.55	0	0
7. Fly-rock	4.8	0	0	0	0	3.75	0	0	0	0	0
8. Noise	2.4	9.24	0	0	0	1.89	0	0	0	24	0
9. Ground vibration	11.2	10.78	0	0	0	0	0	23.31	0	0	0

10.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	53.36
Employment and livelihood of local work force											
11.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.64
Contribution in GDP											
TOTAL	48	55	46	50	49	46	30	70	41	34	80

Figure 9: Final weighted impact scores of all the 4 mines.

The categories' abbreviations and the total weight of each category are listed in Table 10. The modeling takes into account both the environment and human needs and interests, which are the two primary mining-related areas that are affected. Atmosphere, biosphere, hydrosphere, and lithosphere are the four fundamental components of environmental sustainability. The atmosphere has a maximum weight of 200 and protects against air and noise pollution (100 for air pollution and 100 for noise pollution). Due to the dependence of cattle on trees and the Rohiro trees' prohibition in operating areas, biosphere is experiencing biodiversity loss (maximum weight of 100), which endangered several species, including the gugrall (Camiphera Mukul), phoge (Clligonum polygonoides), rohiro (Tecoma undulate), Peeloo (Salvadora persica), Kandi (Prosopis cineraria), and Kombhat (Acacia Senegal)[28]. The hydrosphere, which has a maximum weight of 100 for this study, is connected to water sustainability. The lithosphere, represented in the model by the letter L, is the crust and outermost layer of the earth. The lithospheric part of the environment is responsible for covering aesthetic degradation, above- and below-ground interferences, and soil erosion with a maximum of 400 weights. With 300 weights, the second category is based on the requirements and interests of people. Human safety and health, social interactions and quality of life, and the economy are the issues included in "human needs and interests."

Table 10: Determination sustainability (S) components

Components of Environment (E)		Maximum Possible Scores for E and HNI
A1	Air quality	A _{max} = 2 × 100 = 200
A2	Noise	
B1	Flora and fauna	B _{max} = 1 × 100 = 100
H1	Water quality	H _{max} = 1 × 100 = 100
L1	Use of territory	L _{max} = 4 × 100 = 400
L2	Aboveground	
L3	Underground	
L4	Landscape	
Components of HNI		
HNI1	Human health and safety	L max = 4 × 100 = 400
HNI2	Social relationship	
HNI3	Economy	
Evaluation of Sustainability for the different Mines		
S = E – HNI		

The ultimate environmental sustainability results from Phillips are displayed in Table 11. The real score of environments (E) is displayed in the first column. The second column, however, lists a variety of human needs and interests (HNI). Some mines are in negative indicators in the third column, which displays sustainability values. The mines had a detrimental impact on the environment, according to the sustainability amount's negative sign, while the sustainability amount's positive sign indicates a beneficial impact.

For SMB:

$$E = \frac{[(\sum A_{max} - \sum A) + (\sum B_{max} - \sum B) + (\sum H_{max} - \sum H) + (\sum L_{max} - \sum L)]}{\sum A_{max} + \sum B_{max} + \sum H_{max} + \sum L_{max}}$$

$$E = \frac{[(\sum A_{max} - (A_1 + A_2)) + (\sum B_{max} - \sum B) + (\sum H_{max} - \sum H) + (\sum L_{max} - (L_1 + L_2 + L_3 + L_4))]}{\sum A_{max} + \sum B_{max} + \sum H_{max} + \sum L_{max}}$$

$$E = \frac{[(200 - (70 + 60)) + (100 - 59) + (100 - 52) + (400 - (61 + 57 + 43 + 59))]}{200 + 100 + 100 + 400}$$

$$E = \frac{[111 + 48 + 180]}{800}$$

$$E = 0.42375$$

$$H_{NI} = \frac{(H_{NI1} + H_{NI2}) + (H_{NI3_{max}} - H_{NI3_{actual}})}{\sum H_{NI_{max}}}$$

$$H_{NI} = \frac{(52 + 59) + (100 - 77)}{300}$$

$$H_{NI} = 0.446$$

$$S = E - HNI$$

$$S = 0.42375 - 0.446$$

$$S = -0.02225$$

$E > HNI$ = Sustainable relation ; $E \leq HNI$ = un-sustainable relation

$E (0.42375) < HNI (0.446)$ = un-Sustainable

For AGB2A Mine:

$$E = \frac{[(\sum A_{max} - \sum A) + (\sum B_{max} - \sum B) + (\sum H_{max} - \sum H) + (\sum L_{max} - \sum L)]}{\sum A_{max} + \sum B_{max} + \sum H_{max} + \sum L_{max}}$$

$$E = \frac{[(\sum A_{max} - (A_1 + A_2)) + (\sum B_{max} - \sum B) + (\sum H_{max} - \sum H) + (\sum L_{max} - (L_1 + L_2 + L_3 + L_4))]}{\sum A_{max} + \sum B_{max} + \sum H_{max} + \sum L_{max}}$$

$$E = \frac{[(200 - (80 + 66)) + (100 - 63) + (100 - 58) + (400 - (57 + 67 + 60 + 59))]}{200 + 100 + 100 + 400}$$

$$E = \frac{[91 + 42 + 157]}{800}$$

$$E = 0.3625$$

$$H_{NI} = \frac{(H_{NI1} + H_{NI2}) + (H_{NI3_{max}} - H_{NI3_{actual}})}{\sum H_{NI_{max}}}$$

$$H_{NI} = \frac{(64 + 67) + (100 - 63)}{300}$$

$$H_{NI} = 0.56$$

$$S = E - HNI$$

$$S = 0.3625 - 0.56$$

$$S = -0.1975$$

$E > HNI$ = Sustainable relation ; $E \leq HNI$ = un-sustainable relation

$E (0.3625) < HNI (0.56)$ = un-Sustainable

For ASHAPURA GUINEA RESSOURCES Mine:

$$E = \frac{[(\sum A_{max} - \sum A) + (\sum B_{max} - \sum B) + (\sum H_{max} - \sum H) + (\sum L_{max} - \sum L)]}{\sum A_{max} + \sum B_{max} + \sum H_{max} + \sum L_{max}}$$

$$E = \frac{[(\sum A_{max} - (A_1 + A_2)) + (\sum B_{max} - \sum B) + (\sum H_{max} - \sum H) + (\sum L_{max} - (L_1 + L_2 + L_3 + L_4))]}{\sum A_{max} + \sum B_{max} + \sum H_{max} + \sum L_{max}}$$

$$E = \frac{[(200 - (100 + 60)) + (100 - 74) + (100 - 64) + (400 - (59 + 80 + 60 + 65))]}{200 + 100 + 100 + 400}$$

$$E = \frac{[66 + 36 + 136]}{800}$$

$$E = 0.2975$$

$$H_{NI} = \frac{(H_{NI1} + H_{NI2}) + (H_{NI3_{max}} - H_{NI3_{actual}})}{\sum H_{NI_{max}}}$$

$$H_{NI} = \frac{(74 + 63) + (100 - 63)}{300}$$

$$H_{NI} = 0.58$$

$$S = E - HNI$$

$$S = 0.2975 - 0.58$$

$$S = -0.2825$$

E > HNI = Sustainable relation ; E ≤ HNI = un-sustainable relation

E (0.2975) < H_{NI} (0.58) = un-Sustainable

For Inner Mongolia Bayan Obo mine:

$$E = \frac{[(\sum A_{max} - \sum A) + (\sum B_{max} - \sum B) + (\sum H_{max} - \sum H) + (\sum L_{max} - \sum L)]}{\sum A_{max} + \sum B_{max} + \sum H_{max} + \sum L_{max}}$$

$$E = \frac{[(\sum A_{max} - (A_1 + A_2)) + (\sum B_{max} - \sum B) + (\sum H_{max} - \sum H) + (\sum L_{max} - (L_1 + L_2 + L_3 + L_4))]}{\sum A_{max} + \sum B_{max} + \sum H_{max} + \sum L_{max}}$$

$$E = \frac{[(200 - (50 + 34)) + (100 - 46) + (100 - 46) + (400 - (49 + 30 + 70 + 41))]}{200 + 100 + 100 + 400}$$

$$E = \frac{[170 + 54 + 210]}{800}$$

$$E = 0.5425$$

$$H_{NI} = \frac{(H_{NI1} + H_{NI2}) + (H_{NI3_{max}} - H_{NI3_{actual}})}{\sum H_{NI_{max}}}$$

$$H_{NI} = \frac{(48 + 55) + (100 - 80)}{300}$$

$$H_{NI} = 0.41$$

$$S = E - HNI$$

$$S = 0.5425 - 0.41$$

$$S = 0.1325$$

E > HNI = Sustainable relation ; E ≤ HNI = un-sustainable relation

E (0.5425) > H_{NI} (0.41) = Sustainable

Table 11: Environmental sustainability

Mine	E	HNI	S-Value	S-Level
SMB mine	0.42375	0.446	-0.02225	Un-Sustainable
AGB2A Mine	0.3625	0.56	-0.1975	Un-Sustainable
ASHAPURA GUINEA RESSOURCES	0.2975	0.58	-0.2825	Un-Sustainable
Inner Mongolia Bayan Obo mine	0.5425	0.41	0.1325	Very Weak Sustainability level

Table 11 illustrates the different mining case studied using the Phillips model and environmental sustainability. According to the sustainability assessment, the value of human needs and interests is greater than the value of the environment in all three of Guinea's bauxite mining companies, but the environment is greater than human needs and

interest in the Chinese Rare Earth Element company, though its sustainability level is not that strong too $E(t) < HNI(t) \Leftrightarrow S(t) < 0$. Thus, a relation between the environment and three Bauxite mining operations in Guinea is found to be unsustainable, while a relation between the environment and the only one Chinese company is confirmed to be sustainable.

3.2. Discussions

A qualitative section (Folchi approach) and a quantitative section (Phillips Environmental Sustainability Mathematics (PESM) Model) cover this study's analytical portion. A combination of qualitative and quantitative features supported the semi-quantitative nature of this study. According to four key environmental sectors, the Folchi technique encompassed practically all environmental effect variables. The description of all potential mining parameters and influencing elements is shown in Table 1. The numbering in Table 2 is organized based on how strongly certain parameters affect the indexing process. For the benefit of the reader, this table also describes the particular factor's measurement scale. Understanding Table 3 is crucial for connecting after and before procedures. Folchi technically updates Table 3 with potential maximum, medium, and minimum points. The results of the multiplication are finally shown in Table 6, 7, 8, and 9.

Total scores for each individual element in Table 6, 7, 8, and 9 indicate how much of an actual environmental impact each of these issues has on the four mining companies. The outcome of the Phillips Environmental Sustainability Mathematics (PESM) Model is presented in the second section. The Phillips Environmental Sustainability Mathematics formula is used with anticipated scores and actual scores. In all three Guinean bauxite mining companies, our research shows that environmental impact values are smaller than human needs and interests. The lone Chinese Rare Earth Element mine, in contrast to the other three bauxite mines, and proved a healthy connection with the environment.

To compare the three bauxite mines in Guinea with the Chinese Bayan Obo mine, the average total of scores for the three mines in Guinea is lower. According to the calculations, the Bayan Obo mine is the least damaging to the environment, while the Guinean bauxite mines are the worst. In reality, certain corrective actions must be made for the impacted environmental elements, which are vital for living things (such as air quality, water quality, etc.).

The Folchi technique is the best way for assessing mine operations in Guinea because it takes into consideration a number of environmental criteria that other approaches do not. The method might be used to all mines in Guinea specifically and to all mines globally generally, with careful consideration for its applicability and the surrounding environment. As a result, Guinea may be able to employ the Folchi approach as a tool for environmental management. Applying this approach has a number of advantages, including the ability to simplify difficult analysis by breaking it down into manageable components that can be dealt with one at a time before being reconstituted in a standardized matrix to provide a total magnitude value. This metric may then be applied consistently to compare various mining operations. This is an essential step for using it as a regulatory instrument[36].

The Folchi technique might be improved in that it only captures a moment in time and is therefore temporally constrained. The fact that the implications must be evaluated within a specific time frame raises a number of problems. Here, only environmental issues that are visible at the time of the review are evaluated. Prior to a single review, operators may take steps to influence the assessment. Environmental problems in the early stages or problems that have been partially fixed may go unnoticed. The technique would be more significant if repeated evaluations were conducted throughout time. Site evaluations should preferably be performed regularly and yearly, both on a planned and unannounced basis.

However, the approach as it is now is not ideal for severe accidents or catastrophic mining situations. The Folchi technique also has application in agro-chemical plants and explosives storage facilities. Additionally, efforts are being made to improve and modify the approach to take into account broader situations. In general, the method appears to

have use in a variety of contexts and may be used in the extraction of a variety of geological resources, including petroleum activities[36].

4. Conclusions

There is no denying that Bauxite mining contributes to Guinea's economic growth, but it is also a major cause of socioeconomic problems, soil erosion, and ecological destruction. The Folchi approach makes it possible to quantitatively analyse mining operations, highlighting the consequences of mining on the environment in particular. The Chinese Bayan Obo Rare Earth Element mine is the least environmentally harmful, whereas the Three Guinean Bauxite mines are the most so, according to a comparison of the Three Bauxite mines of Guinea and the One Rare Earth Element mine of China. Future environmental regulatory development in the Republic of Guinea may benefit greatly from the methodology used in the current study. The Folchi model could potentially make it possible for environmental assessments of mining operations to be compared fairly and repeatedly on a global scale.

This study emphasizes the significance of altering the current circumstance, which, without continued maintenance, would result in more harm to the environment and residential areas. Developing ecological restoration is unquestionably one of the top concerns in the research sector. Following the end of extraction activities, it is essential to manage conservation and restoration efforts properly in order to reduce the danger of environmental media contamination and create a system that is sustainable.

Author Contributions:

SANOHOUSMANE and ZHANG Qinli Conceived and design the analysis, Collected the data, contributed data or analysis tools, Performed the analysis and wrote the paper. NINGABO AURELIEN and CONDÉ Fodé Idrissa edited the draft of manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest:

SANOHOusmane, ZHANG Qin-li, Ningabo Aurélien and CONDE Fode Idrissa declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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